

D2.7 Exploitation report of first EERIE outputs

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is a comprehensive and updated summary of all the exploitation achievements of the EERIE project up to date (2025/06/30).

Exploitation is broadly defined as the impact of all project results and production outside the project itself. This includes other scientists, governments, NGOs, media and private companies. The project production is tracked in the Progress & Impact Tracker, while a Zenodo community is used to gather publications under the umbrella of the EU Open Research Repository.

The structure of the current deliverable will follow the current impact of the different result types (datasets, publications and software). Apart from this, it also describes the impact of the contribution of EERIE to the next phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (i.e., CMIP7). It is important to note that it is still early in the project and a much larger impact is expected towards the end of EERIE. We will show how it is beginning to arise and starting to grow, thanks to the open science approach followed by EERIE.

Many important results are not available yet, for example the future projections, the data viewer and the storylines.

1. Datasets

The main datasets produced by EERIE are the model simulations. These are to be published in the Earth System Grid Federation. Notably, the EERIE team also makes them available in near-real time (with some delay) in the EERIE cloud (<https://eerie.cloud.dkrz.de/>). This is an open data server that offers all ESM output through zarr v2. Currently it can be considered a pre-release of the datasets, that can already be used by anyone, even if it is outside EERIE, without requiring any registration or authorization.

Table 1 (below) shows the simulations available as of (2025/06/30), which are a subset of the Phase 1 simulations (M. Roberts et al. 2024) and also include the atmosphere only simulations (C. Roberts et al. 2024b; 2024a). Together, these simulations are the **first ever set of eddy rich multi-model simulations at the centennial scale**, which is considered a result with high scientific potential. They are expected to be completed by September 2025.

Model	Institution	Experiment name
hadgem3-gc5-n216-orca025	Met Office Hadley Centre	eerie-picontrol
hadgem3-gc5-n640-orca12	Met Office Hadley Centre	eerie-picontrol
icon-esm-er	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology/Deutscher Wetterdienst	eerie-control-1950
icon-esm-er	Max Planck Institute for Meteorology/Deutscher Wetterdienst	eerie-spinup-1950
ifs-amip	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	amip-hist-obs
ifs-amip	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	amip-hist-obs-c-lr30-a-0
ifs-amip	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	amip-hist-obs-c-lr30-a-lr30
ifs-amip	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	amip-hist-obs-lr30
ifs-amip	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	amip-ng-obs
ifs-amip	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	amip-ng-obs-lr30
ifs-fesom2-sr	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	eerie-control-1950
ifs-nemo	European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts	eerie-control-1950

Table 1. Simulations available in the EERIE Cloud as of 2025-06-30.

There is no straightforward way of measuring the number of downloads of these files. We know however that the climate modelling community is aware of the existence of these new datasets and preparing or starting to use them. Many scientists from the sibling NextGMS project and from other projects outside EERIE have participated in the joint hackathons organized by the NetGEMS, EERIE and Warmworld projects, where the EERIE cloud has been extensively used.

2. Publications

As of the submission date of this document, the most immediate exploitation indicator of the EERIE data is the number of publications. We divided them into two categories: papers and deliverables. The papers are published in peer review journals which are required to be open access, while the

deliverables are reviewed and approved by the European Commission. Not all deliverables are public, but those which are are published in the EERIE community in Zenodo¹.

2.1 Papers

There are 21 papers already published, with another 7 in preparation, 37 planned and 3 in different stages of the review process. The published papers have been cited 40 times according to Semantic Scholar. Semantic scholar API will be used to keep updating this indicator throughout the project. This number is expected to go up by a lot as the project matures (figure 1).

Figure 1: Total number of citations of EERIE papers as a function of time, starting the 2024-01-01. The data is gathered from Semantic Scholar API².

The statistics of the journals where the publications were accepted also provide a good indication of their quality and impact. The most relevant ones are shown in (table 2, below) according to SCImago³. The indicators tell that these are high impact journals.

¹ <https://zenodo.org/communities/eerie-project>

² <https://www.semanticscholar.org/>

³ <https://www.scimagojr.com/>

Title	Cites / Doc. (2years)	H index
Nature Climate Change	11.98	296
Earth System Dynamics	7.30	70
Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems	4.64	103
Journal of Climate	3.90	344
Geoscientific Model Development	5,00	146
Communications Earth and Environment	8,69	56
Global Challenges	6,92	46

Table 2: Statistics of the scientific journals where EERIE papers have been published. Column one shows the average citations per paper over the last two years (also known as impact factor) and column two the H index, which is defined as the number of papers (h) that have received at least h citations over the whole period.

Another early measure of the impact is the collaboration with different projects. Many EERIE papers are co-authored by researchers outside EERIE. This is reflected in the funding acknowledgements of the papers. The following is a non-comprehensive list of these projects:

Funder	Project name	Code
EU Horizon 2020	PRIMAVERA (PRocess-based climate sIMulation: AdVances in high resolution modelling and European climate Risk Assessment)	641727
EU Horizon 2020	ANDANTE (AttributioN of DynAmic and thermodyNamic components in exTreme weather and climate Events)	846824
NIHR UK	A Novel Extreme Weather Risk Insurance System for Kenya (NEWRISK): Encouraging preparedness, planning, community co-design, and protection of Kenya's health system from the effects of extreme weather	NIHR204850
EU Horizon Europe	BlueAdapt (Reducing climate based health risks in blue environments: Adapting to the climate change impacts on coastal pathogens)	101057764
Academia Sinica (Taiwan)	Development of digital twin for climate change	AS-GCP-112-M03
EU Horizon 2020	USMILE (Understanding and Modelling the Earth System with Machine Learning)	855187
EU Horizon 2020	ESM2025 (Earth system models for the future)	101003536

Table 3: Projects acknowledged in the EERIE papers, apart from EERIE. The list is not comprehensive.

2.2 Public deliverables

The following deliverables have been published in Zenodo. In total they have been downloaded 358 times.

Title	DOI	Unique downloads (zenodo)
D10.1 Report on developments that lead to improvements in ESM throughput	10.5281/zenodo.14353516	18
D9.4 Description of EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations	10.5281/zenodo.14334612	61
D1.1 EERIE Project Management Plan	10.5281/zenodo.14264501	22
D3.1 EERIE Data Management Plan	10.5281/zenodo.8304510	97
D9.3 Description of EERIE idealised atmosphere-only simulations	10.5281/zenodo.14514510	64
D4.1 Phase 1 simulations, including HighResMIP and CMIP6- PI-control simulations	10.5281/zenodo.14288726	43
D6.1 Impact of ocean mesoscale in ocean model biases: an assessment of eddy-rich coupled climate simulations	10.5281/zenodo.14802627	49
D5.1 Report assessing the model simulated eddy statistics	10.5281/zenodo.15689668	4

Table 4: EERIE deliverables published in Zenodo, together with the number of downloads as reported by Zenodo API.

3. Software

Monitoring the usage of the open source software produced by EERIE is challenging as there is no reliable way of tracking downloads by external users. Below we show a table with the Zenodo entries and their number of downloads. Note however that many users are likely downloading the software from Github and not from Zenodo.

Title	DOI	Unique_downloads (zenodo)
CMOR Tables for EERIE Output	10.5281/zenodo.15182101	24
Code for Effect of horizontal resolution in North Atlantic mixing and ocean circulation in the EC-Earth3P HighResMIP simulations	10.5281/zenodo.15064667	16
Data access to EERIE ESM output via intake catalogues: Phase1 plus Hackathon simulations	10.5281/zenodo.14243677	4
FESOM/implicit_filter: Implements first-party support for NEMO Orca grids as well as longitude-latitude grids.	10.5281/zenodo.14285151	38

Table 5: EERIE Software records published in Zenodo, together with the number of downloads as reported by Zenodo API.

4. Contribution to CMIP7 and HighResMIP, and external collaborations

The HighResMIP2 paper (M. Roberts et al. 2025) was published in Jan 2025 as part of work in Task 9.1, planning the direction of work in global high resolution climate modelling for the next WCRP CMIP7 cycle towards the next IPCC report. It is the first published paper in the CMIP7 special issue of GMD, where all the documentation for this project will appear. It involved 35 co-authors across international groups and has already been viewed or accessed nearly 2500 times.

The Data Request that was prepared as part of D3.1 for the EERIE simulations was also used as a basis for the initial HighResMIP2 data request, documenting the variables that groups are meant to supply from the simulations. Eddy-rich ocean models require specific outputs for their analysis: EERIE represents HighREsMIP in the “ocean and sea ice” theme of the CMIP7 data request to ensure that these requirements are taken into account in the CMIP7 data request. These will be documented in the CMIP7 theme publication to be submitted soon to Geoscientific Model Development.

In terms of the CMIP7 FastTrack (AFT) simulations, the Met Office proposes to use the high resolution model developed as part of EERIE to produce AFT simulations and publish them to ESGF. The FastTrack timescale and simulations are designed to feed into the next IPCC report,

and hence having a high resolution contribution to this dataset (most other models are likely to be standard resolution, so around 100km) will be an important step to understand uncertainties in climate change and extremes arising from model resolution.

There are ongoing discussions about using the Met Office simulation data for work outside of EERIE. Marine heatwaves (MHWs) are an impactful ocean extreme, with high ocean surface temperatures leading to impacts on ocean ecosystems as well as influencing atmospheric circulations and storms. Analysis of MHWs is ongoing within EERIE, led by the ETH-Zurich group. Several meetings have also been held with international groups working on MHWs, including in the US and CMCC in Italy, to discuss analysis tools and ways to analyse and exploit the Met Office simulations. Plans are currently being made to make some comparisons with CMCC analysis of MHWs in the Mediterranean Sea.

There are ongoing discussions with a variety of other groups; now that the historical simulations are complete, further discussions will likely lead to additional collaborations.

5. Conclusions and future work

The start of the EERIE project impact has been promising. The open science philosophy, publishing the data and code produced in near real time, has been crucial for reaching it. Further in the project, we plan to continue updating the indicators used in the document and to add new ones. A key aspect to evaluate in the future is the exploitation of the future climate change projections of EERIE, not yet available, by end users and stakeholders.

Acronyms

IPCC - Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change

WCRP - World Climate Research Programme

CMIP - Coupled Model Intercomparison Project

GMD - Geoscientific Model Development journal

HighResMIP - High Resolution Model Intercomparison Project

ESGF - Earth System Grid Federation, where CMIP data is published and made available

CMIP7 FastTrack (CMIP7 AFT)

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